

Mode 2 science: Exploring a common ground of knowledge production in the fields of housing and sustainability

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1. Introduction

The field of housing research is very diverse, theoretically reliant and intertwined with politics, economics, social and, more recently, environmental studies (Matthews, 2016). Sustainability research, on the other hand, is often perceived as a complicated, practice-oriented field that examines the interactions between the economic, social and environmental pillars of society (Purvis et al., 2019). The links between housing and sustainability research are often described as ambiguous and thorny topics, and many scholars refer to them as bifurcated areas of study. As a result, researchers have developed and adapted different approaches to the way knowledge on these two critical areas is perceived and generated. The Mode 2 science is a relatively new concept that calls for the production of context-oriented, scientifically reliable and robust social knowledge, and is most notable for its tendency towards a transdisciplinary approach (Frost & Osterloh, 2003; Gibbons et al., 1994).

This paper is concerned with the methodological issues on how housing and sustainability research and knowledge is presented and produced by those who engage with it. A literature focused exploratory investigation was used to identify the most common methodological issues of both fields. In the end, a reasoned claim was made that the Mode 2 of knowledge production is one of the appropriate approaches to address the methodological challenges of dealing with sustainability and housing. Yet, the claim requires further in-depth investigation leading to a better understanding of the true extent of the problem and the possibility to design an innovative framework for sustainable housing knowledge production.

2. Housing and sustainability methodological challenges

The argument presented in this paper rests on three pillars. The first pillar introduces the methodological principles of Mode 2 science. The second explores methodological issues in housing research, and the third one highlights the prominent debate on sustainability research issues.

2.1 Mode 2 principles

Gibbons et al. (1994), writing about the dynamics of science production, make a clear distinction between Mode 1 and 2 knowledge production. The former is discipline-based and clearly separates 'theoretical' from 'applied', while the latter forms a continuous flow between theory and application to create contextualised outcomes that are influenced by all disciplines concerned (Gibbons et al., 1994). While Mode 1 focuses on the codified component of knowledge, Mode 2 focuses on the tacit components that represent a shift towards a broader social distribution of knowledge (Frost & Osterloh, 2003; Gibbons et al., 1994). Mode 2 dynamics

look at the structure of knowledge from both a homogeneous and a heterogeneous perspective and is therefore not only able to understand and explain the communication between science, society and scientific practitioners, but also to provide a clear framework for the structure of knowledge components (Frost & Osterloh, 2003; Gibbons et al, 1994).

Mode 2 is defined primarily by its inter¹- and transdisciplinary² approach, which shares the same principle with critical research and the postnormal³ sciences (Gibbons et al., 1994). Both academic and social aspects are taken into account to construct the knowledge and methods of the research; validity comes not only from academic peers but also from the extended peer community; furthermore, uncertainty and ignorance are used as a method to verify rather than question the data generated; and a discursive process of opening and closing the focus is followed rather than a strict top-down approach (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009; Frost & Osterloh, 2003; Gibbons et al. , 1994; Wiek & Lang, 2016).

One of the examples of Mode 2 application is the development of an effective healthcare delivery system for the Scottish Health Advisory Service (SHAS) that meets the need for rapid decision-making and a clear but flexible organisational structure (MacLean et al., 2002). Another example is the development of hypersonic projectiles that overcome the challenges of knowledge, material and technology limitations (Gibbons et al., 1994). Both examples raised several issues, including the lack of guidance from existing science, discontinuous prior experience, and the uncertainty of data and results. Applying the Mode 2 approach - as explained by MacLean et al. (2002) for the first example and by Gibbons et al. (1994) for the second - led to the formulation of a structure for collaboration between academics, professionals, scientists and engineers in a trans- and interdisciplinary manner to overcome such challenges and create an effective knowledge base to inform solutions (Gibbons et al., 1994; MacLean et al., 2002).

2.2 Housing research-ers

Writing in 2009, Chris Allen (2009, p. 54) explains that tracking the problems in housing research indicates that the problem is not the lack of a theorising methodology or a justifiable rationale, but that a significant part of the problem lies in the way housing researchers investigate and

¹ Interdisciplinary means that two or more academic disciplines collaborate in an activity that explores a particular topic from different perspectives. See Szostak, R. (2013). The State of the Field: Interdisciplinary Research. *Interdisciplinary Studies*, 1(31), 44-65.

² Transdisciplinary approach enables collaboration between scientific and non-scientific actors and facilitates a systemic approach to address complex challenges. See Pohl, C., & Hadorn, G. H. (2008). Core terms in transdisciplinary research. *Handbook of transdisciplinary research* (pp. 427-432). Springer.

³ Postnormal science is a recently emerged paradigm that investigates-to-evaluate decision-making processes, when facts are uncertain, the stakes are high, solutions are ambiguous and the decision is urgent. See Nogueira, L. A., Bjørkan, M., & Dale, B. (2021). Conducting Research in a Post-normal Paradigm: Practical Guidance for Applying Co-production of Knowledge. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 337.

define the ground of their knowledge in the context of social science knowledge production (Allen, 2009). Allen's (2009) debate draws on Gadamer's (1975) philosophical views on the perception of knowledge and Bourdieu's (2000) discussion of the practices of scholars to conclude that housing research has succeeded in producing adequate theoretical knowledge, but as soon as it believed that this knowledge was superior to other forms of knowledge, particularly '*lived experience*', it declared itself a failure (Allen, 2009; Bourdieu, 2000; Gadamer, 1975). Moreover, it seems that housing researchers have double standards when it comes to questioning research methodology. They doubt the reliability of other scientific methods – especially practice-based research – and overlook the issues of methodology and knowledge organisation in housing, such as the origins and background of applied methodology (Allen, 2008, 2009).

The examination of the most influential works⁴ in the field of housing comes to the same conclusion as Jacques Du Toit et al. (2022), namely that housing scholars focus on the direct applications of approaches but present little to nothing about the context and ground on which these approaches are built (Du Toit et al., 2022). It is also noteworthy that prototypical methodological criteria useful for housing studies are still underdeveloped and lack a clear schematically organised framework (Tobi & Kampen, 2018). Du Toit et al. (2022) add that housing researchers often adopt their methodologies and designs from other social sciences without assessing their applicability to housing research or considering existing proven methodologies (Du Toit et al., 2022; Tobi & Kampen, 2018).

2.3 Sustainability research-ers

Meanwhile, at the level of sustainability research. The work of Wiek and Lang (2016) and Spangenberg (2011) divides sustainability studies into one type that focuses on the descriptive analysis of sustainability problems (descriptive-analytical), while the second type works on developing solutions to these problems and testing their applicability (transformational) (Spangenberg, 2011; Wiek & Lang, 2016). Even though the main methodologies of the two types differ drastically, they share the same risks. Meppem and Bourke's (1999) study was one of the first to point out that sustainability researchers must have a comprehensive understanding of the subject; otherwise, the knowledge produced might not make sense in the context of sustainability (Meppem & Bourke, 1999; Wiek & Lang, 2016). Murphy (2012) clarifies that when researching sustainability, the researcher must explain the context and scale; otherwise, the knowledge produced could be general and serve a limited purpose (Murphy, 2012).

Although the transition from disciplinary to interdisciplinary and later to transdisciplinary approaches is regarded as progress for sustainability science, it poses a greater challenge for

⁴ The examination included: Vestbro et al. (2005) Methodologies in Housing Research; Maginn et al. (2008) Qualitative Housing Analysis; An International Perspective, Studies in Qualitative Methodology; Smith (2012) The International Encyclopaedia of Housing and Home.

knowledge construction (Wiek & Lang, 2016). Jerneck et al. (2011) explain that this requires not only a common ground of terminologies and perceptions, but also a clarification of 'uncertainty' as an indicator of scientific disagreement rather than a data problem (Jerneck et al., 2011). The work of Scerri & James (2010) explains that the coupling of qualitative and quantitative methodologies is crucial to overcome the 'abstract view' of generated knowledge and avoid the exclusive consideration of technical aspects (Scerri & James, 2010). Spangenberg (2011) adds that the tendency towards 'fragmentation' in sustainability research puts the primary goals of 'solving' or 'analysing' at greater risk of generating fragmented knowledge (Spangenberg, 2011).

3. Conclusion

The identified features of Mode 2 directly deal with the presented risks of housing and sustainability research; therefore, the claim that a shift from Mode 1 to Mode 2 is reasonable. However, the question of whether it is necessary to move from the first to the second mode of knowledge production remains unanswered and requires further investigation. But the methodological problems and questions of housing and sustainability research that relate to knowledge production have a threefold connotation:

- The methodological problems of housing and sustainability research can be traced back to the researcher's understanding of knowledge production and the context in which knowledge is produced, and therefore the risk of taking knowledge out of context is high (Allen, 2008). The second problem relates to the principles of methodology construction. As Du Toit et al. (2022) explained, any methodology needs to be comprehensively structured before it can be applied. Therefore, a transdisciplinary methodology needs a review phase, which is often neglected, resulting in some of the methodological specificities being disregarded (Du Toit et al., 2022).
- Leech & Onwuegbuzie (2009) pointed out that for years the choice of methodology seemed to be dichotomous –qualitative and quantitative– and only recently a third choice –mixed– has been introduced, which poses a major challenge for addressing transdisciplinary problems (Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2009). Spangenberg (2011) adds that despite profound changes in nature and society, the disciplinary organisation of scientific knowledge production remains unchanged, especially in housing and sustainability research (Spangenberg, 2011). Therefore, it is necessary to consider Mode 2 to overcome problems in the methodological structure and researchers' approach to knowledge production. However, this change requires its own vocabulary with clearly defined terms to avoid misunderstandings and fragmented knowledge.
- The search for common ground between sustainability and housing research does not only mean finding a common methodology or goal but also extends to the methodological issues that researchers in both fields face. The existence of methodological differences is a natural outcome of the specificity of the fields. However, developing an innovative framework that recognises these differences and responds to rapid societal and technological change is crucial and needs further exploration.

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